

CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR TOWARDS PACKAGED FRUIT JUICES IN PRAYAGRAJ DISTRICT OF UTTAR PRADESH.

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Abstract

To gain an in depth understanding of the consumer buying behaviour towards packaged fruit juices in the region of Prayagraj, this study was undertaken. It also focuses on understanding the attitudes of consumers, when buying this product. This study also throws light on why and how do people buy, consume packaged fruit juices. The study was conducted by using a questionnaire. This was used to gather data from consumers for conducting research. For the consumer, convenience sampling with a judgemental basis was used. Convenience samples were drawn from the Chaka Block of Prayagraj district. The sample size selected was 140 for the research. The researcher tries to explore the different factors and parameters, which affects the purchase behaviour, perception, attitude and decision making of the consumer. This study thus, will help in designing and developing effective marketing strategy. Since convenience sampling is used therefore this study does not represent the whole younger generation. Moreover, it is conducted in the region of Prayagraj alone, so the result of research may vary if it is conducted in any other city. Sampling error may also take place and the questions asked may not be comprehensive.

Keywords: - Consumer decision, perception, attitudes, research, fruit juices.

Introduction

In India, the juice market grew at a compound annual growth rate of more than 10% during a six-year period. By the completion of the predicted period in 2027, the juice industry is expected to increase at a CAGR of more than 11 percent. The fruit juice sector is also dominant, with mango-flavored drinks being the most popular in the Indian market (Businesswire, April 8, 2022). The fruit juice industry is expected to increase significantly in the next years due to the numerous health advantages. Consumers with health consciousness are shifting from packaged juice products to natural juice or home-made juice, which is much healthier and having no artificial flavors and preservatives, as opposed to the fruit drinks market. Dabur, Parle Agro, PepsiCo, Coca Cola, and other corporations have demonstrated their presence in the Indian market.

Increased consumption of fruit juices from street vending sites and restaurants appears to be partly attributed to lifestyle changes and concomitant urbanisation, as well as growing prosperity. Consumption of fresh fruit and fruit juice has several advantages. Fruit juices are pure and vibrant liquids with tremendous healing properties. They are not only refreshing, but they are also high in antioxidants. Fruit juices high in vitamins help to build the body and prevent the degradation of skin, flesh, glands, and organs (T. BindhyaDhanesh, V. Indira, 2018).

There are three categories in which the market of packaged fruit juices is segmented:

1. Drink which has a maximum fruit content of 30% called as Fruit drinks.
2. Drink having fruit content between 25% to 90% called as Nectar drinks, and
3. Drink which have fruit content of 100% called as fruit juices

Materials And Methods

Sampling procedure- Multistage stratified random sampling procedure was adopted for the present investigation to select the ultimate unit of the sample. The Selection of District, block, villages and respondents were done randomly.

Stage 1: Selection of the district - A total of 75 districts in Uttar Pradesh from which prayagraj district was purposively selected to

study about the consumer buying behaviour towards packaged fruit juice.

Stage 2: Selection of block - Selection of the block is the second stage of sampling. Out of 23 blocks present in Prayagraj districts, Chaka was selected purposively.

Stage 3: Selection of villages- complete list of the village of selected block was obtained from the block development office of the concerned block. There are 137 villages in Chaka block. Then all the villages are arranged in order and 5% villages were selected randomly.

List of selected villages in Chaka block

1. Chaka
2. Cheonki
3. Dandi
4. Gangotri nagar
5. Mahewa Patti Paschim Uparhar
6. Mahewa west
7. Marauka uparhar

Stage 4: Selection of Respondents - Respondents were selected from these seven villages of chaka block. 20 Respondents were randomly selected from each village.

Likert Scale:

A likert scale is a rating scale used to assess opinions attitudes, or behaviours. Likert scale are popular in survey research because they allow you to easily operationalise personality trade or perception.

To collect data, you present participant with likert type question or statement and a continuum of possible responses, usually with 5 or 7 items. Each item is given a numerical score so that the data can be analyze quantitatively.

A Likert scale assumes that the strength/intensity of an attitude is linear, i.e. on a continuum from strongly agree to strongly disagree, and makes the assumption that attitudes can be measured.

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1	2	3	4	5
Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree

Results And Discussion**Importance of brand**

Table shows that majority of the respondents (81 percent) was considering the brand name as an important part while selecting a fruit juice, however 19 percent disagree and believe that brand name is not relevant when choosing fruit-based beverages.

Importance of Brand

Importance of Brand	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	113	80.71%
No	27	19.28%

Significance of fruit juices

Table shows the significance of fruit juices, when asked how essential fruit-based drinks are in their everyday lives. Nearly 23 percent of respondents said fruit juices was very important on daily basis. About 27 percent respondents consider fruit juices to be an essential

component of their daily diet. Nearly 31 percent respondents are not sure about the importance of fruit juice in their daily diet. Out of 140 respondents, 11 percent of the respondents do not consider fruit juices in their daily needs to be important, while 8 do not consider it at all.

Significance of fruit juices on daily needs

Significance of fruit juices on daily basis	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Not important at all	11	7.85%
Not Important	16	11.42%
Neutral	43	30.71%
Important	38	27.14%
Very important	32	22.85%

Factors influence buying decision

Table represents factor influencing buying decision of the respondents. The number of elements that affects purchasing behaviour of the respondents. Family and friends were most important factors that influencing respondents' buying decisions regarding fruit juice with 61 percent. Second most important influencing factors for purchasing fruit juice was Television/Radio.

The Internet playing important role in decision making of the 15 percent respondents' decision making. Word of mouth influencing about 10.71 percent respondents regarding buying decision. Nearly 10 percent respondents' decision was influenced by the Newspaper/Magazine for buying decision. Remaining 1.42 percent respondents were influenced by some other sources for making decision regarding purchasing of fruit juice.

Factor influencing buying decision

Factor influencing buying Decision	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Television/Radio	27	19.28%
Newspaper/Magazine	14	10.00%
Family/Friend	61	43.57%
Word of mouth	15	10.71%
Internet	21	15.00%
ther	2	1.42%

Factor influencing buying Decision

Level of involvement in day-to-day household Purchasing decision

Table shows that, according to the responses, about 65 percent of the respondents was making decision of purchasing without anyone’s involvement. Nearly 18 percent respondents were consulting with

others like with their friends and family, while making the purchase decision, whereas 12 percent of the respondents were playing no role in decision making while purchasing a fruit beverage. About 5 percent of respondents don’t know about their role in purchasing fruit juices.

Level of involvement in day-to-day household Purchasing decision

Level of involvement in day-to-day household purchasing decisions	Number of Respondants	Percentage
I make decision alone	91	65.00%
I generally consult others while making the decision	25	17.85%
I just Accompany others to the shop and play no role in decision making	17	12.14%
Do not know	7	5.00%

Type of outlet preferred

Types of outlets preferred for purchasing fruit juice is presented in Table shows most of the respondents (69 percent) was preferred the traditional groceries or kirana stores for purchasing Fruit based beverages. Nearly 28 percent respondents was preferred modern retail outlets or big retail stores for purchasing fruit juice. Only 3 percent respondents were prefer to buy online.

Type of Outlet preferred for purchasing fruit juice

Level of involvement in day-to-day household Purchasing decision

Outlet from where you regularly purchase packaged fruit Juice	Number of Respondants	Percentage
Traditional Groceries/ Kirana Store	97	69.28%
Modern Retail outlets or Big Retail Stores	39	27.85%
Online	4	2.85%

Type of Outlet preferred for purchasing fruit juice

Frequency of purchasing fruit juice

Table represents frequency of purchasing fruit juice by the respondents. Table shows a substantial proportion of respondents were buy fruit-based beverages on a regular basis (at least one time a week) or one time every 2-3 weeks. This clearly shows that the purchasing of fruit-based beverages was high on their priority list and was enjoyed on a regular basis. Only 11 percent of respondents purchase fruit-based beverages on rarely basis.

Frequency of purchasing fruit juice

Frequency of purchasing fruit juice	Number of Response	Percentage
Once a week or more often	86	61.42%
Once every alternate week	21	15.00%
Once in a month	6	4.28%
Once every two or three months	11	7.85%
Very rarely	16	11.42%

Frequency of purchasing fruit juice

Quantity preferred

Table shows a significant proportion of respondents were purchase fruit-based beverages in 200/300 ml packs. Around 16 percent of respondents was preferred 500/600 ml bottles, whereas 26 percent respondents were preferred large size or family packs of 1 liter.

Preferred Quantity

Preferred Quantity of Packaged Fruit Juices	Number Of respondents	Percentage
200-300ml	81	57.85%
500-600ml	22	15.71%
1L or above	37	26.42%

Preferred Quantity

Factors influencing in choosing a particular brand

Table shows the most important considerations by the respondents for selecting a specific packed fruit juice were pricing, reputation, display/merchandising, location/nearness and Ambience with 22 percent, 21 percent, 16 percent, 14 percent and 14 percent respectively, followed by service with 10 percent. The occasion and other factors are the least essential variables influencing channel selection.

Factors influencing in choosing a particular brand

Factors for choosing a particular brand	Number of respondents	Percentage
Pricing	31	22.14%
Ambience	12	8.57%
Location/Nearness	19	13.57%
Service	14	10.00%
Display	23	16.42%
Reputation	29	20.71%
Occasion	7	5.00%

Others	5	3.57%
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Factors for choosing a particular brand

Conclusion

After performing an observational study and actively interacting with 140 respondents in Prayagraj district, it was observed that packaged fruit juices were becoming an important part of households whether it is consumed for taste or as a source of refreshment. It was discovered that there is a really a large potential for fruit related beverages market, because of tremendous number of benefits provided by juices. Households are aware of the market opportunities, and fruit-based beverages have a high market acceptability. Fruit beverages have begun to become an important part of households' everyday necessities during social occasions and during entertainment. The Indian beverage industry offers several opportunities for new products and product modifications due to increased health and nutrition attention, changing lifestyles, and higher earnings.

Fruit drinks have become an important component of Indian families, particularly in urban and semi-urban areas, because they provide vibrancy and energy, as well as relationship and nutritional benefits. During the purchasing process, many factors influence a customer's purchasing behaviour and attitude, including demographic characteristics such as age, marital status, monthly salary, profession, and so on, as well as other factors such as the influence of friends and family, advertising through various media, and so on. These primary factors should be properly addressed in order to establish an ideal market space, because catering to the demands of a client is critical in today's world in order to construct a strategic marketing plan that grows market share.

Major Findings

Majority of the respondents were influenced by friends/family to buy packaged fruit juice. Brand of fruit juice played a crucial role in choosing a fruit juice the respondents.

Majority of the respondents were preferred to take decisions alone. Most of the respondents were buy fruit juices from traditional groceries or kirana store.

Most of the respondents consume at least once a week and the most preferred quantity they buy is 200/300 ml.

Pricing of a fruit juice product was influenced the most while choosing a fruit juice followed by Pricing and Brand reputation.

Majority of the respondents purchase packaged fruit juices once a week or more often.

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